

Impact of composition changes of alumina-rich slags on the corrosion of refractories found in steel ladles

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Abstract

Changes in the steelmaking process can lead to changes in slag composition and consequently in the refractories' corrosion mechanisms. This paper aims to investigate the corrosion of a resin-bonded MgO-C brick using three different slags. It focuses on two different aspects: the change of slag basicity by addition of SiO₂, and the addition of 10 wt.% of MnO. Two corrosion tests were conducted for this purpose. First, slag pellets were put on top of brick pieces to reproduce the conditions at the interface between the brick and the slag. The samples were fired at 1450°C for 1h in oxidizing and reducing atmosphere. Second, pellets consisting of magnesia powder mixed with each slag in a 3/1 wt.% ratio, were also fired at 1450°C for 1h. After firing, the samples were observed and characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The results indicate that the slag with the lower basicity leads to a more extensive corrosion. Moreover, the corrosion by the slag containing 10wt.% MnO leads to the formation of a MgO layer at the surface of the bricks.

1. Introduction

Due to new demands from the steel market, the steelmaking process needs to evolve in order to stay competitive. One area of development focuses on increasing the manganese content in the steel to give it higher mechanical properties compared to regular steel. Consequently, the amount of MnO in the slag will increase due to exchanges between the steel and the slag. Yet, an increase in the manganese content of the slag might lead to changes in the slag properties. Moreover, these changes can also modify the slag corrosive attack on the refractories, especially at the slag line. However, only few papers focus on the effect of manganese during corrosion could be found.

Van Ende et al.¹⁾ studied the impact of MnO in silica-rich slag on the corrosion of one pitch-bonded MgO-C brick. They performed finger test using three slags with MnO content varying from 1 to 26 wt.%.

They found out that MnO can participate in carbon intrinsic oxidation but this effect is limited due to the formation of a (Mg, Mn)O solid solution in MgO grains which deprive the slag of its MnO content. They also stated that the solid solution formation has no impact on the refractory wear.

Zhang et al.²⁾ studied the corrosion of magnesia by two different slags containing FeO and MnO. They found out that, in some cases, FeO and MnO diffuse in the MgO grains and form a magnesiowustite layer at the surface of the MgO grains; as the magnesiowustite grains were larger than the initial grains, the penetration of the slag was limited.

Um et al.³⁾ studied the stability of MgO-C refractories in slags for ferromanganese alloy making. Using the rotating finger test, they evaluated the corrosion rate of MgO-C bricks against seven silica-rich synthetic slags including one containing 30 wt.% of MnO. They found out that the presence of MnO in the slag increases the MgO-C corrosion rate due to two factors. First, MnO from the slag can oxidize C from the matrix according to:

This leads to a quicker decarburization of the bricks. Second, the presence of MnO in the slag decreases the slag melting point. Thus, MgO dissolution is favoured because Mg diffuses faster in the slag.

Nevertheless, the literature on the role of MnO in the corrosion of refractories in alumina-rich slags is not extensive. Therefore, this study investigates the impact of MnO addition to an alumina-rich slag on a commercial resin-bonded MgO-C brick. Additionally, tests were performed with a higher SiO₂ content in the slag to study the impact of basicity modification.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1. Materials

For this study two materials were used: a commercial resin-bonded MgO-C whose composition is given in Table 1 and a pure MgO powder with a particle size below 125 µm.

Table 1: Composition of the refractory brick

wt.%	MgO-C
MgO	96.9
Al ₂ O ₃	0.2
SiO ₂	0.5
CaO	1.9
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.3
C	10

Additionally, three synthetic slags were prepared using reagent grade powders. Their compositions are given in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Composition of the slags

wt.%	Standard	10 wt.% SiO ₂	10 wt.% MnO
Al ₂ O ₃	41.4	38.9	37.3
CaO	51.8	48.6	46.6
SiO ₂	4.1	10.0	3.7
MgO	0.6	0.6	0.6
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.1	1.9	1.9
MnO	0.0	0.0	10.0
Basicity (C/S)	12.6	4.9	12.6

2.2. Experiments

Two types of corrosion test were performed. The first one, the contact test, consisted in putting a pressed slag pellet on a brick piece to observe what is happening at the interface between the slag and the refractory. This test was conducted in oxidizing atmosphere (air) and in reducing atmosphere. The reducing atmosphere was obtained by putting each sample in a closed carbon crucible with carbon grains added.

The second one, the pellet test, consisted in mixing the MgO powder with each slag in a 3/1 wt.% ratio to determine what reactions can take place when MgO is in excess compared to slag.

For both tests, the samples were fired at 1450°C for 1h with a heating rate of 5°C/min.

After the firing, the samples obtained with the pellet test were crushed for XRD analysis (D8 ADVANCE Theta/Theta) and the samples obtained with the contact test were cut in two, polished, and then observed with an SEM coupled with EDS (SEM FEI NovaNanoSem 200 and LEO Zeiss Type 440i-Oxford Link Isis, germanium detector)

3. Results and discussions

The samples obtained with the contact test are presented in **Fig. 1**. In oxidizing atmosphere, the carbon is partly oxidized and the whole decarburized area is infiltrated by slag whereas none of the part containing carbon is infiltrated. At the top of the samples, where the slag pellets were in contact with the bricks, destruction of the samples' microstructure is observed. This comes from gas formation or

decarburization. During removal, the gas bubbles have to go through the liquid slag which has infiltrated the sample. This phenomenon is responsible for the microstructure destruction at the top. The same phenomenon is not observed at the bottom part of the sample, probably because the slag reaches this area by capillary effect after the gas has left.

In reducing atmosphere, the slag stayed on top of the sample; hence the observed infiltration is limited. It takes place between the grain and the carbonaceous matrix when debonding is present and within the magnesia grains' porosity. It also appears that the slag containing manganese wets the sample more as its contact angle is lower and it spreads on the brick more as seen in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1 Pictures of MgO-C sample corroded in reducing and oxidizing atmosphere respectively using a) - b) standard slag; c) - d) 10 wt.% SiO₂ slag; e) - f) 10 wt.% MnO.

To obtain more information on the samples from the contact test, SEM with EDS observations were performed. The results are presented in **Fig. 2**.

For all samples, it can be observed that MgO aggregates dissolve inside the slag. Because the slag is far from saturation, the amount of corrosion is significant.

In the case of the samples corroded in the reducing atmosphere, the magnesia aggregates' dissolution into the slag is especially visible for the sample dissolved by the standard slag and the 10 wt.% SiO₂ slag when considering the distance – a few tens of microns - between the top of the carbon matrix and the top of the aggregates. It appears that the dissolution with 10 wt.% SiO₂ slag is more extensive since the distance is about two times

higher.

Fig. 2 Micrographs of MgO-C sample corroded by the different slag in reducing and oxidizing atmosphere respectively using a) - b), standard slag; c) - d), 10 wt.% SiO₂; e) - f), 10 wt.% MnO.

The saturation concentration of MgO decreases with increasing basicity^{3),4)} and it has been demonstrated previously that the dissolution of MgO in slag is controlled by diffusion, thus the dissolution rate can be described by³⁾:

$$j = D(C_{sat} - C_{slag})/\delta^* \quad (2)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient, C_{sat} is the saturation concentration of the species considered, C_{slag} is its effective concentration in the melt and δ^* is the effective boundary layer for diffusion. The basicity of 10 wt.% SiO₂ slag is lower so the saturation concentration is higher which leads to an increase in the corrosion rate.

For the corrosion by 10 wt.% MnO slag, the corrosion rate is hard to estimate because the corrosion is not homogenous. In some areas, the corrosion depth is significant while in other it is limited.

It can also be noticed that a dense MgO layer formed on top of the carbon with the 10 wt.% MnO slag in the oxidizing and the reducing atmosphere. This phenomenon has already been observed by several authors^{5), 6), 7)}. It is due to the reduction of MgO by C according to reaction (3) when the partial pressure of oxygen is low, for example, in the pores in the oxidizing atmosphere. Then the Mg vapor oxidizes again when it reaches the surface of the bricks and forms a dense MgO layer.

In the oxidizing atmosphere, this reaction is beneficial as it limits the slag infiltration inside the refractory. In practice, this layer formation will be

beneficial as it will protect the carbon from oxidation when the brick is in contact with air.

Moreover, for all the samples in the reducing atmosphere, but especially with the standard slag, metallic particles can be observed. They consist of Fe_{metal} and are the result of the reduction of Fe₂O₃ or MnO by carbon^{2), 6)} according to reactions (5) and (6):

In the case of the standard slag, it seems that the metallic layer covers in part the carbon matrix. For the brick corrosion resistance, this reaction is detrimental as it leads to the carbon matrix disappearance and facilitates slag infiltration.

Additionally to SEM observations, XRD analysis was performed on grind pellets from the powder test. The results are presented in **Fig. 3**. The reactions, that proceeded inside the pellet, show that different phases form with the different slags. This is interesting because the conditions of the pellet test are close to the conditions of the slag infiltrated in the pores of the samples.

In all the samples, the main phase remains MgO. However, for the sample prepared with the 10wt.% MnO slag, the peaks associated with MgO, exhibit a shift which can indicate the incorporation of Mn ions inside MgO.

Concerning the other phases, with the standard slag, they mainly consist of mayenite (Ca₁₂Al₁₄O₃₃) and larnite (Ca₂SiO₄). No other phases, including those containing MgO, could be found.

For the slag containing 10 wt.% SiO₂, calcium aluminium magnesium silicate

($\text{Ca}_{38}\text{Mg}_{1.04}\text{Fe}_{1.44}\text{Al}_{23.52}\text{Si}_{36}\text{O}_{156}$) and akermanite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{Mg}[\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7]$) phases are found. The detection of phases containing MgO in this sample is possible due to the higher MgO dissolution in this slag compare to the standard one. The higher MgO dissolution in this slag would be consistent with the observations from the contact test: more MgO is dissolved in contact with 10 wt.% SiO_2 slag, and with the literature: the MgO dissolution is higher in low basicity slag^{3), 4)}.

For the 10 wt.% MnO slag, Akermanite is also found. The phase detection is possible because the amount of MgO that diffuses into the slag is higher with this slag than with the standard slag. Indeed, the formation of the (Mg,Mn)O solid solution is due to the counter diffusion of Mn-Mg according to the reaction (4); the Mn ions diffusion inside the periclase grains leads to the Mg release in the slag.¹⁾

Fig. 3 Diffractograms of the three mixtures raw material with slag.

Fig. 4 Evolution of the calculated slag viscosity with MnO content.

According to Van Ende et al.¹⁾, the replacement of Mg ions by Mn ions inside the periclase will not impact the periclase corrosion resistance against

slag. However, the MnO removal from the slag will prevent carbon oxidation by MnO and, according to viscosity calculation with the software Factsage 6.4, will lead to a slag viscosity increase, as seen in Fig. 4, which is beneficial.

To better understand the effect of MnO addition, more test needs to be realized. This will be the following of this paper. Tests at higher temperature as well as dynamic test will be performed.

Conclusion

The different corrosion mechanisms were observed. They were mainly depended on the slag chemical composition. The SiO_2 increase in the slag leads to a corrosion rate increase of MgO-C bricks.

The addition of MnO to the slag might be beneficial if an increase in the quantity of the formed MgO layer is confirmed. It would be interesting as it would limit the slag penetration inside the bricks and limit carbon oxidation. However, the MnO addition to the slag decreases its viscosity which could be detrimental if the dense MgO layer formation is not confirmed.

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